

Waveform Comparison under Hardware Limitations for 6G Sub-THz Communications

Le Hang Nguyen, Volker Braun, Hardy Halbauer and Thorsten Wild
Bell Laboratories, Nokia, Magirusstraße 8, D-70469 Stuttgart, Germany
Le_Hang.Nguyen@Nokia-Bell-Labs.com

Abstract—Sub-Terahertz communication is a key enabling technology to deliver ultra-high rates up to Terabit/s - one of 6G envisioned goals. However, hardware limitation and impairments set practical challenges in realizing real-world networks operating at such high frequency range. In this paper, based on simulation findings, we analyze the performance of different single- and multi-carrier transmission concepts in the sub-Terahertz range under hardware impairments and limitations, both from a today's New Radio (NR) up-scaling perspective, and whether it is best to deviate from the straightforward up-scaling into a new design. We therefore focus on the following sub-Terahertz network determinants: the signal peak amplitude characteristics, the phase noise of the local oscillators and the quantization effect of the analog-to-digital-converter. Insights drawn from the analysis are considered to make proposals on the signaling concepts for a practical access network design in the sub-Terahertz range. We also demonstrate how further improvement can be harvested considering signal amplitude variation optimized constellation modulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tremendous amount of work has been carried out in the earlier phase of 5G to identify the suitable transmission candidate for the available spectrum both below and above 6GHz [1][2]. The decision was made, in 3GPP New Radio Release 15 [3] (NR), in favor of multi carrier Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing with cyclic prefix (OFDM) and its Discrete Fourier Transform spread variant (DFT-S-OFDM). Moving towards sixth Generation of Communication System (6G), ultra high data rates in the order of Tbit/s (or at least 100 Gbit/s) are envisioned. The new available huge spectrum in Terahertz (THz) and sub-THz range provide means to deliver the targeted data rate. However, sub-THz communications set new constraints and requirements on the system design. The increase in the free space path loss at these high frequencies requires high gain large antenna arrays to compensate for the reduced signal power. It is also known that the efficiency of power amplifier (PA) devices, operating at sub-THz range, is extremely limited [4]. Further, the use of wide bandwidths, at least in the range of several GHz, requires circuit components capable of processing high data rates. The power consumption of these components, e.g. Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC), scale with the sampling rate and the covered bandwidth [5]. In combination with the high number of transmitter chains, all these mentioned issues inevitably lead to extremely power hungry systems and make power efficiency a key requirement to be considered in designing such 6G systems. In this investigation we seek for a sub-THz system design of a

practical access network which can efficiently be implemented with respect to both spectrum and energy usage. At the transmitter side, the PA is identified as the most dominant component in the power consumption. At the receiver side the main contributor to the power consumption is the ADC. Furthermore, local oscillators in the signal synthesizer inherently exhibit phase noise (PN) which increases by 6 dB for every doubling of the carrier frequency and becomes prohibitive in sub-THz range, without any further countermeasures. These main contributors define the rule how the sub-THz physical layer has to be designed. Different transmission technologies are differently sensitive to these physical layer determinants. We therefore assess the performance of various waveforms under the above mentioned constraints. Our contribution is to provide a holistic examination on the performance of different waveforms in a practical future access system which operates in sub-THz band under real-world impairments. We will furthermore depict whether a deviation from a straightforward upscaling of 5G NR is appropriate for designing a beyond 5G system w.r.t. design focus, waveform, numerology and modulation.

We start out on waveforms deployed in current NR standard OFDM and DFT-S-OFDM, considering the possibility to upscale NR. In addition, IEEE standard 802.15.3d [6] has developed a physical layer that spans 50 GHz of bandwidth, between 275 and 325 GHz. Single carrier (SC) and on-off keying are the choice as transmission mode. Despite the different deployments, the requirements on hardware efficiency as well as constraints on transmission technology are common. That promotes SC transmission with Frequency Domain Equalization (SC-FDE) as a further interesting candidate for the investigations.

This paper is structured as follows: In section II we shortly recap the signaling structure and the corresponding implementation complexity of the waveform candidates. In section III, based on simulation results, the performance of the waveform candidates is assessed and discussed under the constraints of linear power amplifier, the phase noise impacts of the local oscillators and the quantization effect of the ADC converter. Section IV summarizes the discussions. Section V concludes and gives an outlook to future investigations.

II. PARAMETER SETTINGS AND PERFORMANCE METRICS

We consider a wideband system operating in the D-Band at 120 GHz. The parameters used in this investigation mostly

Fig. 1. Block diagram of DFTSO, OFDM and SC-FDE.

follow NR design. Sub carrier spacing Δf is scaled by 2^μ from the basis Δf of 15 kHz, where μ is the numerology and is of positive integer $\mu = [0,1,2,3,\dots]$. For the simulations a Δf of 960 kHz is assumed which results in a symbol duration $T_s = 1/\Delta f$ of 1.04 μs . Efficient Low Density Parity Code (LDPC) with code rate of 3/4 is applied and an overhead of 7% for cyclic prefix (CP) is assumed. Currently there is no sub-THz propagation channel model available, except few preliminary measurements. In this study Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) is considered. Nonetheless, CP overhead of 0.3 dB is considered in E_b/N_0 , taking into account its presence in the transmissions. In NR the maximal number of allocated resource blocks (RB) N_{SC}^{RB} , is 275 RBs. When considering a full band allocation with Δf of 960 kHz, OFDM occupies a channel bandwidth of 3.17 GHz. To reduce DFT computational complexity NR constrains allocated bandwidth of DFT-S-OFDM transmission to some radix combinations (detailed later in section III). It is set in this study to 256 RBs, equaling to a channel bandwidth of 2.95 GHz. SC-FDE uses full band for transmissions, which results in a bandwidth of 3.93 GHz. SC-FDE transmission is further filtered with a Root Raise Cosine pulse shaping filter (RRC), applying a roll off β of 0.3, to limit the spectral response. Table I summarizes

Parameters	Value
Carrier frequency [GHz]	120
FFT size	4096
Occ. BW [GHz]	O:3.17 /D:2.95 / S:3.92
Coding	LDPC 3/4
RRC β	0.3 (SC-FDE only)
Cyclic Prefix [%]	7
PT-RS [%]	3
Nr. T_x, R_x	1,1

TABLE I
PARAMETERS USED IN THIS STUDY. O, D AND S STAND FOR SC-FDE, OFDM AND DFT-S-OFDM RESPECTIVELY. PT-RS: PHASE TRACKING REFERENCE SIGNAL.

the relevant parameters used in this study. (Note that the single transmitter and receiver includes the required analog beamforming.)

Since different waveforms have different effective bandwidths, for a fair comparison we considered the 99% power containment bandwidth BW_{eff} using the spectral density at the transmitter and calculate the Spectral Efficiency (SE) from the measured BLER as follows

$$SE = \frac{(1 - BLER) * R}{BW_{eff}} \quad (1)$$

where R is the data rate. R and BW_{eff} values are summarized in Table II.

	OFDM	DFT-S-OFDM	SC-FDE
Data rate [Gbits/s]	2.22*n	2.06*n	2.75*n
Eff. bandwidth [GHz]	3.90	3.90	4.47

TABLE II
DATA RATE AND EFFECTIVE BANDWIDTH OF THE CONSIDERED WAVEFORMS. n : THE NUMBER OF MODULATED BITS PER SYMBOL (2,4 & 6 BITS FOR QPSK,16QAM AND 64QAM, RESPECTIVELY)

III. WAVEFORM CANDIDATES

Current NR defined OFDM as the general transmission mode. It was also agreed that DFT-S-OFDM can be used as an alternative in the uplink (UL) for power saving reason at the User Equipment (UE). These two legacy waveforms are to be compared with SC-FDE using block based single carrier transmission. In this paper we thus focus on those obvious candidates, while knowing that there may be further disruptive alternatives [7] which have to be considered in a later comparison. Figure 1 shows the block diagram of the three waveforms. As can be seen DFT-S-OFDM has the highest processing effort. Compared to OFDM it needs an additional DFT operation for each transmit and receive side. In NR, to reduce DFT computational complexity, the resource allocation is constrained to certain radix combinations of $2^{\alpha_2}, 3^{\alpha_3}, 5^{\alpha_5}$ where $\alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_5$ are non-negative integers [3]. It is further based on resource blocks (RB), such that

all combinations of $2^{\alpha 2}$, ('power of two'), are ruled out. For example, an assignment of $2^9 = 512$ subcarriers is not possible since it's not a multiple of 12. Similar to OFDM, DFT-S-OFDM offers frequency multiplexing capability. SC block transmission SC-FDE possesses the most simple processing chain at the transmitter side and requires in total as many FFT operations as OFDM. To confine the spectral pattern a pulse shaping filter is required. Root-raised-cosine (RRC) is generally used for this purpose which is known to cause *SE* loss and increase the Peak-To-Average-Power Ratio (*PAPR*). Unlike the NR legacy waveform, SC-FDE does not offer an efficient frequency multiplexing possibility, other multiplexing forms need to be applied instead. This is, however, quite unlikely that the BSs will have to simultaneously serve numerous different UEs in the same directions, considering the fact that large propagation loss has to be compensated for and hence very narrow beams, in the order of few degrees, are applied in sub THz/THz communications.

IV. IMPACT DUE TO HARDWARE LIMITATIONS

A. Peak to Average Power Ratio (*PAPR*)

As already observed in NR, FR2 hardware is far less energy efficient than FR1. Moving towards the sub-THz frequency range, this issue becomes an ultimate challenge for hardware component development. Recent analysis on the power consumption of RF front end transceiver [8] has identified the PA as the most power consuming component in the transmitter. It is therefore highly desired to allow PAs to operate at their optimal efficiency, e.g. with backoff as low as possible. *PAPR* is an important design parameter, since it directly affects the PA efficiency. The relation between PA efficiency and *PAPR* is given as

$$\eta_{PA} = \eta_0 10^{-(PAPR/20)} . \quad (2)$$

where η_0 is 0.5 for linear PAs [9]. Measures to further drive PAs efficiency outside the linear region is proposed but is not included in this study. Figure 2 shows the complementary cumulative density function (CCDF) of the *PAPR* level of the waveform candidates for 256-QAM modulation. *PAPR* computation considers the baseband analog sampled signal. High *PAPR* is a well-known characteristic of multi carrier transmission like OFDM (red curve) and stemming from the superposition of the individual subcarriers carrying the signals during the FFT operation. The larger the FFT size the higher the resulting *PAPR*. For the studied case a *PAPR* of 12.8 dB is reached at 10^{-5} of the CCDF.

In contrast, single carrier block transmission like SC-FDE features a desirable *PAPR* characteristic, avoiding the FFT operation in the transmissions. Envelope fluctuation introduced by signal modulation and pulse shaping filter determine the *PAPR* level in that case. In this study a RRC filter was applied to confine the signal spectrum. Depending on the shape of the RRC (i.e. the roll-off factor) the *PAPR* level varies. An increase by 0.8 dB in *PAPR* can be observed when changing β from 0.5 to 0.3 (blue triangle vs. blue circle in figure 2). Compared to multi-carrier transmission (blue vs. red) a reduction up to

5.5 dB in *PAPR* can be achieved.

In case of DFT-S-OFDM, the additional DFT before the iFFT spreads out the phase and helps to reduce the *PAPR* level (triangle black in Figure 2). The *PAPR* reduction amounts to 2.6 dB compared to OFDM case, but still up to about 3 dB higher compared to *PAPR* level of SC-FDE case. Allowing DFT and iFFT size to be equal, iFFT is canceled out by the DFT operation and the *PAPR* of DFT-S-OFDM takes on the pure SC characteristics, without filtering (black circle vs. blue star). Note that in real implementation some sort of upsampling and pulse or spectral shaping will be needed here. A high *PAPR* level forces an operation with back-off to safely be away from the saturation point and hence to avoid output signal distortion. That leads to less output power, greater loss of power efficiency, less battery lifetime at the user-side, as well as range restrictions for the base stations. A *PAPR* reduction of 5.5 dB against OFDM and 3 dB against DFT-S-OFDM (of 3072 size), when applying SC-FDE signaling, can beneficially be translated into to a highly desired range extension in sub-THz scenario. Under assumption of free space path loss in line of sight conditions a gain of 3dB in the signal power corresponds to approximately a factor of 1.4 in range extension.

Fig. 2. *PAPR* characteristics of OFDM (red), SC-FDE (blue) and DFT-S-OFDM (black) for 256QAM modulation. Different rolloff factors β for SC-FDE and different DFT sizes for DFT-S-OFDM are also plotted

B. Phase Noise

The higher the carrier frequency the more severe the impact of the phase noise (PN) on the communication links. It is therefore important to analyze the sensibility against PN for the waveform candidates, in particularly, in conjunction with realistic compensation algorithms with tolerable complexity. PN is due to the time varying characteristics in frequency of the local oscillator (LO) and depends therefore on the quality of the implemented LO. A power spectral density (PSD) is commonly used to define the spectral purity of a LO. It specifies the noise power in 1 Hz band at a specific offset from the carrier frequency f_c . For the phase noise modeling in this study a multi pole/zeros model as suggested in [11] is

used where $PSD0$ is the power spectrum at zero frequency, $f_{z,n}$ and $f_{p,n}$ are zero and pole frequencies. $\alpha_{z,n}$ and $\alpha_{p,n}$

$$S(f_o) = PSD0 \frac{\prod_{n=1}^N 1 + (\frac{f_o}{f_{z,n}})^{\alpha_{z,n}}}{\prod_{n=1}^N 1 + (\frac{f_o}{f_{p,n}})^{\alpha_{p,n}}} \quad (3)$$

describe the zero and pole points power, respectively. These parameters are to be chosen such that the model matches the PSD shape of the implemented LO. For the transmitter side, an approximate of the PSD of the 20GHz wideband RF synthesizer LMX2595 from Texas Instrument is used which is currently available for mmwave applications [10]. For the receiver side, the model with the associated parameters set as defined in [11] Table 6.1.11.2-1 is applied. The noise power is scaled up to the needed f_c of 120GHz according to the rule $20\log(f_c/f_{ref})$, where f_{ref} is the reference frequency of the PSD measurements. Figure 3 displays the PSD of the PN models deployed in this study.

In NR, Phase Tracking Reference Signals (PT-RS) may be

Fig. 3. Phase noise PSD of the TI LMX2595 synthesizer (black, square) applied at the base station and the 3GPP model applied at the UE (blue, circle).

transmitted for phase tracking and compensating purpose at the receiver. PT-RS can be inserted in a subcarrier for every 2nd or 4th PRB of an OFDM symbol, and up to every OFDM symbol can carry a PT-RS signal [12]. From this, the maximal PT-RS overhead amounts to 4.1%. On multi carrier signals, PN causes common phase error (CPE) and inter-carrier interference (ICI) [13]. A PT-RS signal with a distributed pattern as designed in NR for OFDM is mainly meant to correct the CPE part. Based on the received PT-RS an average phase de-rotation value can be calculated and applied for all subcarriers. In this manner, CPE contribution can simply and effectively be suppressed. In contrast, ICI estimation requires knowledge on correlation of each subcarrier to many other neighbored subcarriers and therefore needs a much higher computational effort compared to CPE estimation. Higher subcarrier spacing can be deployed to reduce ICI contribution. This however implies shorter CP. Assuming NR frame structure, it results in lowered robustness against delay spread and higher out of band radiation. Further,

the flat fading condition within a single subcarrier, prerequisite for simple OFDM one tap equalizer, is no longer valid for too large subcarrier spacings. Subcarrier spacing, as well as suitable CP length, need to be designed according to the channel properties of the targeted deployment scenarios and are subject to further study.

For DFT-S-OFDM transmissions, PT-RS are inserted in groups of 2 or 4 time samples and there can be 2,4, or 8 groups in each symbol [3]. Thanks to the block wise structure in time domain, PN (CPE and ICI contribution) can be estimated using a simple least square algorithm, an averaging and interpolation for the data position value. It should be emphasized that the computational effort here is comparable with the CPE estimation and suppression in the OFDM case.

For SC-FDE, the same PT-RS pattern as DFT-S-OFDM is assumed, and identical PN compensation algorithm is applied. Taking into account the processing complexity of the compensating algorithms, robustness against PN for different waveform can be assessed in a fair manner.

Figure 4 shows the $BLER$ and SE as a function of the required

Fig. 4. $BLER$ (upper) and SE (lower) of the waveform candidates: OFDM: red, DFT-S-OFDM: black and SC-FDE: blue. PN is compensated applying the described algorithms.

E_b/N_0 for all waveform candidates applying PN estimation and compensation algorithms described above. Note that the number of deployed PT-RS for different waveforms with different occupied channel bandwidth is appropriately scaled, such that the same PT-RS overhead is accounted for all waveform candidates (approx. 3.1%). PT-RS insertion follows NR-design with distributed and block-wise pattern for CP-OFDM and DFT-S-OFDM/SC-FDE, respectively. QPSK, 16-, 64-QAM are considered. OFDM clearly suffers from the strong ICI caused by PN, except for low modulation order

TABLE III
ACHIEVABLE SE FOR OFDM, DFT-S-OFDM AND SC-FDE UNDER PN
IMPACT CONSIDERING SIMPLE COMPENSATION ALGORITHM.

Modulation	QPSK	16QAM	64QAM
OFDM	0.85	1.65	1.79
DFT-S-OFDM	0.79	1.58	2.37
SC-FDE	0.92	1.84	2.76

QPSK. OFDM benefits from the higher number of available PT-RS for averaging compared to DFT-S-OFDM and SC-FDE, such that a better noise suppression can be achieved. This effect is more pronounced and hence observed in the low E_b/N_0 QPSK region. In the DFT-S-OFDM and SC-FDE case, PN can be well compensated using the algorithm described above. The $BLER$ performance of the two waveforms exhibits similar behavior, the achieved SE is however higher for SC-FDE. This is explained by the higher data rate and the spectral broadening of a RRC filter with a β of 0.3. The achieved SE for all the waveform candidates are summarized in the Table II

C. Quantization

Fig. 5. $BLER$ as a function of quantization bit number for SC-FDE (upper plot) and DFT-S-OFDM (lower plot).

At the receiver side the ADC converter is the component with non-negligible contribution to the overall system power consumption. Its power consumption doubles with each additional quantization bit, hence ADCs with low resolution are desired. On the other hand limited resolution degrades the achievable system performance. For an optimal energy efficiency the number of quantization bits should not be higher than needed.

We analyze now jointly the impact of quantization and PN on the transmit signal for the waveform candidates. PN effect is compensated as described above. Uniform quantizer with equal spaced steps is considered. The amplitude distribution of OFDM and DFT-S-OFDM can be considered as zero mean Gaussian. Typically for this type of quantizer input, the dynamic range utilization of the ADC is approximately optimized applying a clipping at 4σ , where σ^2 is the variance

of the distribution. The block transmission SC-FDE signal is formed by the shape of the RRC filter and its distribution is more confined compared to the multi carrier OFDM and DFT-S-OFDM. An adaptive quantizer is therefore deployed, which adjusts the dynamic range and step size to the input amplitude on symbol basis. Figure 5 exemplarily shows the $BLER$ as a function of the number of quantization bits for SC-FDE and DFT-S-OFDM waveform. QPSK, 16- and 64QAM cases are considered. SC-FDE shows a more robust behavior in case of very coarse quantization (e.g. less than 4 bits for QPSK case). Increasing the number of quantization bits the performance of DFT-S-OFDM approaches that of SC-FDE. This behavior can be explained by the clipping mechanisms, which becomes more profitable with higher number of quantization levels. Exemplary consider now the 64QAM case from figure 5. $BLER$ performance for SC-FDE is sufficient with 4 quantization bits (black curve in the upper plot) whereas DFT-S-OFDM needs 5 bits (red curve lower plot) for the same $BLER$ performance. According to the figure of merit based power consumption model as described in [16], that means that the ADC power consumption in SC-FDE transmission case can be of a factor of 2 lower compared to DFT-S-OFDM waveform case.

D. PAPR optimized modulation

As pointed out in section IV-A the PAPR level in case of SC-FDE is strongly determined by the variation in the signal amplitude. Constraint to constant envelope constellation minimizes the PAPR level. Phase Shift Keying (PSK) or Continuous Phase Modulation (CPM) techniques provide means to generate such low PAPR signal. These are however of low spectral efficiency or high implementation complexity. We consider a properly designed Amplitude Phase Shift Keying (APSK) with constraint on the amplitude variation as the optimal tradeoff between performance and PAPR reduction. The selected constellation consist of 2 rings with 4 points on the inner and 12 on the outer ring (cf. inset in plot (b) of Figure 6). The ratio between the ring radii r_{inner}/r_{outer} is 0.6 and gray mapping is used. The constellation points are further normalized to unit energy. As before, a RRC filter with β of 0.3 was applied. Figure 6 shows $PAPR$ and $BLER$

Fig. 6. a) CCDF of $PAPR$; b) $BLER$ performance of SC-FDE waveform modulated with ringQAM constellation. Inset: 2 rings constellation used in the study.

performance of the selected constellation. Results of standard square 16QAM are also plotted as reference. It can clearly be seen that the improvement of 1.8 dB in $PAPR$ outweighs

the loss of 0.3 dB in *BLER* performance. When considering the required PA backoff a total improvement of 1.5 dB can be harvested for further coverage extension. Performance tradeoff of further constellation shaping is the subject of future work.

V. DISCUSSION

The most prominent show-stopper for OFDM is its *PAPR* characteristic. That requires that the PA works with power back off and forces a system to operate with a reduced average signal transmit power. Consequently, it intensifies the severe range impact, which is one of the challenges of high frequency due to the increase in the path loss. For OFDM to work in the sub-THz range, *PAPR* reduction methods without compromising other performance metrics are of eminent importance. To combat PN related ICI issue, low complexity algorithms are needed. A first step has been made in proposing a new PT-RS pattern and method with reduced complexity [14] [15]. But much more efforts are required to make OFDM attractive for sub-THz band communications.

As a variant of OFDM the NR legacy DFT-S-OFDM shows - besides the backward compatibility to 5G - improvement in *PAPR* characteristics and robustness against PN. However, the highest *PAPR* reduction can be achieved allowing the pre-DFT to be of the size of the followed iFFT. This would lead to a seamless transform from DFT-S-OFDM to SC-FDE transmission. As mentioned in section III, current NR DFT-S-OFDM transmissions exclude a resource allocation of 'power of two' due to the RB based scheduling rule (based on a multiple of 12 subcarriers). Relieving from this constraint allows to exploit an additional gain of 3 dB in *PAPR* and further complexity reduction. Hence for 6G systems, when considering an evolutionary waveform approach with DFT-S-OFDM, the NR numerology paradigms should be completely reconsidered. Allowing DFT-spreading sizes with 'power of two' can be achieved when RBs are formed with 'power of two' in numbers of subcarriers (e.g. 16). Depending on allocation size, a full band allocation transitions the Fig. 1 block diagram of DFT-S-OFDM into the much simpler SC-FDE block diagram leading to reduced computational complexity and the above discussed additional *PAPR* gains.

A sub-THz system applying SC-FDE alone, e.g. independently from existing NR standard, provides several advantages: high *SE*, low *PAPR*, robustness against PN, less sensitive to ADC coarse quantization, low processing complexity, and - as demonstrated - high potential for further *PAPR* optimization, e.g. by modifying the modulation constellation, thus a better power efficiency. But it will have to resign from the frequency multiplexing capability. As already pointed out above, this is a mild trade-off due to the marginal probability that several UEs happen to be in the same narrow 3D beam angle and simultaneously require for services. Other multiplexing means like space, time, polarization remain available.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study we have discussed the choice of suitable waveform for sub-THz, considering the possibility to upscale 5G

NR. From our discussion on the candidate results and related processing building blocks, regarding convergence of DFT-S-OFDM into SC-FDE, we also show where to deviate best from simple NR upscaling. Namely, DFT spreading requires a 'power of two' and should converge for full-band allocation to the FFT size, which simplifies complexity and improves *PAPR*. This can only be achieved when the 12-subcarrier RBs are replaced by a 'power of two' value, e.g. 16 subcarriers. This allows to switch between DFT-S-OFDM and SC-FDE transmission and preserves frequency multiplexing capability of DFT-S-OFDM. We have also demonstrated the potential for further performance improvement in case of SC-FDE, exploiting *PAPR* optimized modulation constellations. This and other efficient and practical measures to further optimize the 6G physical layer are subjects to be tackled in the near future.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been partly funded by the European Commission through the H2020 project Hexa-X (Grant Agreement no. 101015956).

REFERENCES

- [1] 3GPP R1-162199, "Waveform Candidates".
- [2] Gerzaguet, R., et. al., "The 5G candidate waveform race: a comparison of complexity and performance", J Wireless Com Network 2017, 13 (2017).
- [3] 3GPP TS 38.211 V16.3.0 (2020-09), 3rd Generation Partnership Project; Technical Specification Group Radio Access Network; NR; Physical channels and modulation".
- [4] Hua Wang et al. , "Power Amplifiers Performance Survey 2000-Present,". Online https://gems.ece.gatech.edu/PA_survey.html
- [5] A. Mezghani and A. Nassek, "Modeling and Minimization of Transceiver Power Consumption in Wireless Networks", International ITG Workshop on Smart Antennas, 2011
- [6] V. Petrov, et. al., "IEEE 802.15.3d: First Standardization Efforts for Sub-TeraHertz Band Communications toward 6G", IEEE Communications Magazine, Nov. 2020
- [7] P. Neuhaus, M. Dörpinghaus, H. Halbauer, V. Braun and G. Fettweis, "On the Spectral Efficiency of Oversampled 1-Bit Quantized Systems for Wideband LOS Channels", 2020 IEEE 31st Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications, 2020, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/PIMRC48278.2020.9217277.
- [8] H. Halbauer, T. Wild, "Towards power eEfficient 6G sub-THz Transmission", to be published in Proceeding EUCNC 6G summit 2021
- [9] S. R. Biyabani, R. Khan, M. M. Alam, A. A. Biyabani and E. McCune. "Energy Efficiency Evaluation of Linear Transmitters for 5G NR Wireless Waveforms". IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking 2019, pp. 446454.
- [10] Texas Instrument. Data sheet LMX2595. Online <https://www.ti.com/rf-microwave/rf-plls-synthesizers/overview.html>.
- [11] GPP TR 38.803 v. 14.2.0, "Study on New Radio (NR) Access Technology; RF and co-existence aspects," Tech. Spec. Group Radio Access Network, Rel. 14, Sept. 2017
- [12] 3GPP TS 38.214, NR; Physical layer procedures for data, 2018.
- [13] P. Robertson and S. Kaiser, "Analysis of the effects of phase-noise in orthogonal frequency division multiplex (OFDM) systems", Proceedings IEEE International Conference on Communications 1995.
- [14] V. Syrjala, T. Levanen, T. Ihalainen, and M. Valkama, "Pilot Allocation and Computationally Efficient Non-Iterative Estimation of Phase Noise in OFDM", IEEE Wireless Communications Letter Vol. 8, No. 2, April 2019
- [15] O. Tervo, T. Levanen, K. Pajukoski, J. Hultkonen, P. Wainio and M. Valkama, "5G New Radio Evolution Towards Sub-THz Communications," 2020 2nd 6G Wireless Summit (6G SUMMIT), 2020, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/6GSUMMIT49458.2020.9083807.
- [16] B. Murmann, "ADC Performance Survey 1997-2018", Online <http://web.stanford.edu/~murmann/adcsurvey.html>